

Detection of protein oligomers with nanopores

Robert I. Horne^{1†*}, Sarah E. Sandler^{2,3†*}, Michele Vendruscolo^{1*}, Ulrich F. Keyser^{2*}

¹*Centre for Misfolding Diseases, Yusuf Hamied Department of Chemistry,
University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK*

²*Cavendish Laboratory, Maxwell Centre, Department of Physics,
University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK.*

³*Wyss Institute, Harvard University, Boston MA, USA*

†Authors contributed equally

*Corresponding authors

RIH email: rih29@cam.ac.uk

SES email: Sarah.Sandler@wyss.harvard.edu

MV email: mv245@cam.ac.uk

UFK email: ufk20@cam.ac.uk

Abstract

Powerful single-molecule approaches have been developed for the accurate measurement of protein oligomers, but they are often low throughput and limited to the measurement of specific systems. To overcome this problem, nanopore-based detection holds the promise of providing the high throughput, broad applicability, and accuracy necessary to characterize protein oligomers in a variety of contexts. Nanopores provide accuracy comparable with that of state-of-the-art single-molecule detection methods, but with the added potential for fast and accurate measurements that may be amenable to industrial-scale manufacture. Key to enabling this expansion is combination with other emerging technologies such as DNA-nanostructure tagging, machine learning enabled signal analysis and innovative detection device manufacture. Together, these technologies could enable widespread adoption of nanopore-based sensing in oligomer detection, revolutionizing diagnostics and biomarker detection in protein misfolding diseases.

[H1] Introduction

Protein oligomers have key roles in cellular functions, structural stability and signal transduction (**Figure 1a,b**)¹⁻⁴. The aberrant formation of misfolded protein oligomers is associated with numerous diseases (**Figure 1b-f**) and is particularly relevant to neurodegenerative disorders⁵⁻⁷. In many of these conditions, healthy brain cells are progressively damaged, due in part to the presence of misfolded protein oligomers (**Figure 1f**)⁸⁻¹³. While functional oligomers form highly ordered, stable complexes that can be studied by well-established methods, misfolded oligomers exhibit heterogeneity in structure and composition, and are dynamic and transient^{14,15}. Thus, misfolded oligomers have proven particularly challenging to characterize, despite their importance as disease biomarkers and therapeutic targets^{5-7,16-22}. This challenge calls for innovative, interdisciplinary approaches. Significant efforts have already been directed towards the development of techniques to achieve this goal. Single-molecule fluorescence detection methods make up most of these efforts but require fluorescent tagging and cannot yet be applied generally or at scale^{23,24}. Therefore, there remains a need for a technique that can fulfil a broad array of oligomer detection roles.

51

52 Rapid biomarker screening with higher predictive validity is a particularly acute need,
53 not only for the creation of diagnostic tools, but also as a scalable method of measuring
54 drug efficacy in screening pipelines²⁵. Current clinical endpoints, such as clearance of
55 larger amyloid aggregates in the case of Alzheimer's disease (**Figure 1d**), do not
56 correlate well with patient outcome^{18,26-29}. Evidence suggests that misfolded oligomer
57 levels are more closely linked with toxicity and disease progression in a variety of
58 neurodegenerative conditions^{16,24}. Therefore, quantification of oligomer populations
59 could make a more effective predictor of disease state and drug efficacy. As we will
60 discuss in this review, nanopore-based detection is currently well placed to fill this
61 methodological gap³⁰⁻³⁴.

62

63 The aggregation-prone peptides and proteins that have been most commonly
64 investigated via nanopore-based methods are amyloid- β ($A\beta$)^{35,36}, tau^{37,38} and α -
65 synuclein (αS)^{17,30,39-41}. All three are implicated in neurodegenerative diseases, $A\beta$
66 and tau most prominently in Alzheimer's disease (**Figure 1d**), and αS in Parkinson's
67 disease (**Figure 1e**). The mechanisms of toxicity of oligomers in disease are an area
68 of intense study, and are best understood for αS (**Figure 1f**). αS oligomer formation,
69 which can be induced by reactive oxygen species (ROS), is further enhanced in the
70 presence of cardiolipin, which is present in higher proportions in mitochondrial
71 membranes⁴². Oligomer interactions with respiratory complex I and the mitochondrial
72 membrane then result in depolarization, leading to increased ROS formation. ROS
73 induces further oligomerization in a feedback loop. Escalating mitochondrial damage
74 leads to sustained opening of the mitochondrial permeability transition pore (mPTP)
75 and activation of caspase 3-dependent apoptosis⁴². Considerable work has therefore
76 been directed at αS oligomer detection in the nanopore field^{17,23,30,39,41,43-45}. αS
77 represents a useful test case for prototype technologies designed to study protein
78 oligomers. αS is surprisingly soluble for an amyloidogenic protein due to its abundance
79 of charged groups, rendering it easy to purify and maintain control of aggregation.
80 Techniques successfully applied to αS can be expanded to more challenging
81 aggregation systems.

82

83 **[H1] Principles of nanopore-based detection**

84

85 Biological nanopores (**Figure 2a**) and those made with solid-state materials (**Figure**
86 **2b,c**) can be harnessed for measuring protein oligomers. In both cases oligomers are
87 driven through a nanoscale aperture between two chambers of salt solution using
88 electric fields. As molecules move through the pore, the liquid containing the salt ions
89 is displaced. The drop in liquid volume in the nanopore correlates to an increase in
90 resistance and thus a drop in the measured current (**Figure 2d,e**). This current drop
91 can provide information about the charge, molecular weight and conformation of the
92 analyte⁴⁶. Signals also arise when biomolecules interact with the surface of the pore
93 as this process similarly induces current changes.

94

95 These systems can be tailored to enhance detection. The intersection of nanopore-
96 based sensing and oligomer characterization requires many chemical insights, not
97 only in understanding the biochemistry of protein modifications that lead to
98 oligomerization, but also the optimization of the nanopore itself, which is highly reliant
99 on chemical factors. For biological pore systems, these include the lipid membranes
100 used to embed the pores, biochemical modification of the pore proteins to optimize
101 analyte interactions, the ionic conditions of the buffer system, and the development
102 and improvement of the motor proteins that enable passage through the pore
103 (translocation). For solid-state pore systems, these include the ionic conditions of the
104 buffer system and design of the chemistry and microstructure of the pore surface for
105 analyte interactions. The pore architecture itself can also be tailored which is not
106 possible for biological nanopores.

107

108 Based on the current rate of progress, nanopore-based sensing has potential to impact
109 not only our fundamental understanding of protein oligomers and their properties, but
110 also areas of biotechnology and medicine where protein oligomer detection is
111 essential to both the diagnosis of diseases and evaluation of novel therapeutic
112 approaches. Alternative technologies to nanopore-based detection shall be briefly
113 introduced to provide a benchmark for nanopore-based methods. For a detailed review
114 of these alternative technologies in the context of oligomer detection see Vendruscolo
115 and co-workers²². For a recent review of protein oligomerization mechanisms see
116 Limbocker and co-workers⁴⁷. For a prior review of nanopore methods in this area see
117 Balme and co-workers⁴⁸, which delves into the technical aspects of each nanopore

118 class in detail and compares their relative strengths in detection of prion-like protein
119 aggregates that can trigger the misfolding of other proteins.

120
121 Here we aim to give a broader overview of progress in the field, advantages over other
122 measurement approaches, and demonstrate where the opportunities lie for expansion
123 of this technology. For the latter aim we focus on the combination of nanopore-based
124 sensing with DNA nanostructure labeling and machine learning expedited signal
125 analysis, as well as the development of one-pot aggregation measurement devices
126 such as the real time fast amyloid seeding and translocation (RT-FAST) platform⁴⁴.
127 These methods hold great promise for the field of biomarker detection in diseases
128 featuring oligomeric proteins. We conclude by discussing areas for improvement in
129 this field, which include the limited size of biological nanopores, the balance between
130 signal-to-noise and pore diameter in solid-state nanopores, complex data analysis,
131 and the current low production capacity of solid-state nanopores with highly
132 reproducible diameters.

133 134 **[H1] Bulk methods for oligomer detection**

135
136 Bulk methods helped to establish the aggregation mechanisms of amyloidogenic
137 proteins^{49,50}. The dynamics of the oligomer populations can be calculated indirectly by
138 fitting measurements of endpoint amyloid fibril formation measured via amyloid-
139 binding dyes such as thioflavin T (ThT)⁵¹⁻⁵⁶. Previously, this approach involved the
140 collection of samples at different points in the aggregation process and measurement
141 via size exclusion chromatography and mass spectrometry (SEC/MS) or enzyme-
142 linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) (**Figure 3a**). Although this procedure is
143 quantitative, it suffers from low throughput and technical challenges. The readout is
144 the bulk monomer concentration at a given elution volume, for a certain time point of
145 the aggregation. The elution volume corresponds to the size of the oligomers, with
146 larger species eluting first. Nonetheless the detection of bulk monomers in discrete
147 sample fractions means that information about the size and shape distribution of the
148 oligomers is lost. Non-perturbative single molecule methods provide faster and more
149 informative results.

151 A successful use of bulk aggregation data in the clinic is the real-time quaking-induced
152 conversion (RT-QuIC) diagnostic assay, an aggregate amplification method (**Figure**
153 **3b**)^{57,58}. The RT-QuIC assay takes patient samples and determines whether they can
154 seed the aggregation of the protein implicated in the suspected disease. The
155 importance of this assay is illustrated by a recently published study announcing the
156 first effective biomarker detection method for Parkinson's disease, and the subsequent
157 roll out of the SYNTap® test which is based on RT-QuIC⁵⁹. Difficulties with this
158 approach include the length of the experiment (many hours) and the noise introduced
159 by biological sample components that makes accurate back-calculation of the initial
160 amyloid quantity challenging. A further drawback is the requirement for cerebrospinal
161 fluid (CSF), which necessitates invasive procedures. Research is under way to use
162 less invasive samples such as blood, where oligomer levels are very low. Hence, there
163 remains a need for more efficient and accurate solutions to this problem²².
164 Nonetheless, while RT-QuIC may not readily give the precise oligomer levels in a
165 sample, it can differentiate samples from patients with or without disease with ~90%
166 accuracy, thus representing a promising diagnostic method for protein misfolding
167 diseases.

168

169 **[H1] Single-molecule methods for oligomer detection**

170

171 Many single-molecule techniques besides nanopores have shown notable results in
172 the characterization of oligomer distributions²². These methods have enabled the
173 examination of oligomer distributions under conditions closely resembling
174 physiological settings. In the following section we review them, highlighting both their
175 successes and their limitations.

176

177 **[H2] Confocal two-color coincidence detection (TCCD)**

178 TCCD is a single-molecule technique that enables the detection of oligomers
179 containing monomers tagged with one of two fluorophores, by measuring molecules
180 diffusing through a confocal volume⁶⁰ (**Figure 4a**). Oligomers can be distinguished
181 from monomers as they contain mixtures of both fluorophores and so 2 simultaneous
182 excitations can be detected⁶⁰. An open challenge, however, is that diffusion biases
183 can result in a decrease in detection efficiency with increasing oligomer size.

185 [H2] Fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS)

186 FCS has a similar limitation, as it records the fluorescence fluctuation signal resulting
187 from fluorescent molecules diffusing across the focal volume⁶¹ (**Figure 4b**). In this
188 case, all proteins are labelled with a single fluorophore, and the fluctuation of the
189 fluorescence within a confocal volume corresponds to speed of movement of tagged
190 particles and therefore their size. This information is gathered by analyzing the auto-
191 correlation curves of fluorescence fluctuation⁶¹.

192 [H2] Single-molecule total internal reflection fluorescence (TIRF)

193 TIRF is not limited by diffusion, but the reliance on photobleaching of fluorophore
194 tagged monomers leads to a small oligomer detection limit⁶² (**Figure 4c**). For a given
195 oligomer, upon excitation, each fluorophore tag photobleaches in a stepwise
196 fluorescence reduction. However, signal change becomes exponential rather than
197 stepwise above 10-mers, and so photobleaching events become harder to discern⁶².

198 [H2] Super-resolution Points Accumulation for Imaging and Tracking (sPAINT)

199 sPAINT can record both the spatial position and emission spectrum of single dye
200 molecules simultaneously, allowing one to super-resolve an image⁶³ (**Figure 4d**). As
201 sPAINT makes it possible to map hydrophobic states, it has been used to observe
202 both reductions in hydrophobicity in oligomeric vs fibrillar samples as well as the
203 variation in hydrophobicity in aggregates⁶³. This technique can provide essential
204 information about the structure of the oligomers.

205 [H2] Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

206 AFM generates images of the aggregate structure, based on scanning a 1-10 nm wide
207 cantilever tip over monomers, oligomers and fibrils immobilized on a surface⁶⁴ (**Figure**
208 **4e**). The deflection of the cantilever as it tracks across the surface is measured via a
209 laser directed at the cantilever head. Changes in the cantilever head height are
210 detected by the reflected laser beam. This technique can also be combined with
211 infrared spectroscopy to give information about the secondary structure (α -helical, β -
212 sheet, random coil) of the immobilized aggregates.

213 [H2] Micro free flow electrophoresis (μ FFE)

218 μ FFE has demonstrated its ability to determine oligomer populations in the presence
219 of specific secondary nucleation inhibitors^{23,65} (**Figure 4f**). In μ FFE, fluorescently
220 tagged aggregate mixtures are injected into a microfluidic device and the fluid stream
221 is separated by an electric field. The degree of deflection and the photon count of each
222 particle are proportional to its size and charge. The deflection allows the separation of
223 monomers from oligomers and the photon count gives a measure of the number and
224 size of the oligomers at a particular time point.

225 226 **[H1] Advantages of nanopores in oligomer studies**

227
228 A significant drawback of all the above methods is the low throughput compared to the
229 potential for nanopores³¹. The sampling method in both TCCD and FCS also relies on
230 particles diffusing through a confocal volume, which biases the result towards particles
231 small enough to diffuse with enough speed to be measured. In nanopores,
232 measurements are diffusion-independent, as molecules undergo electrophoretic
233 forces which push them through the pore. TIRF is limited to relatively small aggregate
234 detection, as photobleaching events become indistinguishable beyond approximately
235 10 fluorescently labelled monomers in an oligomer. Solid-state nanopores can sample
236 a much greater range of the size distribution, provided their diameters are tuned
237 appropriately. Both sPAINT and AFM provide highly detailed information about
238 aggregate structure, but require immobilization of samples on a surface, which may
239 introduce artifacts, and measurement times are lengthy. Nanopores are solution based
240 and could potentially measure a greater range of protein sizes and conditions
241 depending on the nanopore system and labelling techniques used.

242
243 Finally, μ FFE has many of the benefits of nanopore-based techniques (solution based
244 and not diffusion limited), and there is no requirement for tailoring to the size
245 distribution of interest in comparison to nanopores, where the pore diameter must be
246 appropriately customized to allow particles to go through the pore. However, as it is a
247 fluorescence-based technique, the number of different samples that could be
248 measured in a single device, or the multiplexing capacity, is limited to 4-5 owing to the
249 wide emission spectra of most fluorophores. As we will explain in the subsequent
250 sections, the multiplexing capacity of nanopores is orders of magnitude higher than is
251 possible for fluorescence-based techniques.

252

253 [H1] Biological nanopores for label-free investigations

254

255 Protein sensing can be achieved using unmodified nanopores and targets of interest,
256 or via functionalizing either the target or the pore itself to improve measurement
257 resolution^{66,67}. The solution conditions can also be tailored to improve detection⁶⁸. An
258 example of biological pore customization is the engineering of the outer membrane
259 protein G (OmpG nanopores) to include epitope tags, such that the pore itself
260 becomes a binding target. Tags are incorporated into the flexible, solvent-exposed
261 loops of OmpG, and antibody binding causes changes in the nanopore signal, allowing
262 direct measurement of antibody epitope selectivity⁶⁹. However, as the benefit of
263 leaving the analyte or nanopore untagged is the simplicity in the set up, this approach
264 has been adopted in the larger proportion of biological nanopore studies into protein
265 oligomer sensing.

266

267 Efforts to study oligomers in nanopores began with label-free methods, owing to their
268 simplicity and flexibility, as well as an initial lack of effective compatible labelling
269 methods^{35,70-72}. Nanopores are capable of providing protein sequence or aggregate
270 level information, depending on the pore diameter^{17,40}. The smaller pore diameter limit
271 of biological pores (1.4 nm at its lowest extent in α -hemolysin⁷³) has meant that these
272 studies focused on monomeric protein or peptide fragments^{40,74}. Smaller diameters
273 lead to higher resolution, meaning different amino acid residues can be discerned.
274 However, to investigate oligomer structures and distributions observed in various
275 aggregating systems, larger pore diameters are generally required. While
276 investigations into synthesizing larger biological nanopores are ongoing, only solid-
277 state nanopores are currently capable of full oligomer structure determination given
278 their diameter can be tailored to the distribution of interest, which is not currently true
279 of biological nanopores.

280

281 Biological nanopores nonetheless have some notable advantages over solid-state
282 nanopores. Foremost amongst these is higher structural reproducibility from pore to
283 pore. Second is a relative lack of fouling, whereby analyte adheres to the pore surface
284 and clogs the pore. This is a substantial problem for solid-state nanopores, although

285 it can be addressed via functionalization of the pore surface. Protein synthesis is also
286 an easier method than synthetic fabrication for large scale production of pores of the
287 narrow dimensions required for high resolution. Studies using biological nanopores
288 therefore fulfil an essential role in providing information about the aggregation process
289 as a function of sequence level information and monomer dynamics. This capacity can
290 be used in diagnostics, and in understanding oligomerization propensity and
291 mechanisms of toxicity in disease³⁹. It is also possible to characterize aggregation, to
292 an extent, by tracking the number of bumping events, whereby large oligomers impact
293 the pore but do not translocate^{35,75}. Because of the high sensitivity, studies involving
294 biological nanopores focus on identification of post translational modifications (PTMs)
295 and mutations in peptide fragment mixtures derived from the digestion of full-length
296 proteins with proteases (**Figure 5a,b**).

297
298 Changes to the protein sequence arising from mutations or PTMs impacts aggregation
299 mechanisms and disease^{40,74,76}. In an example of PTM detection in nanopores,
300 glycosylation of generic peptides was detected and quantified in a modified
301 fragaceatoxin C (FraC) nanopore, offering a potentially cheaper and faster alternative
302 to mass spectrometry^{74,77}. Slowing down translocations is key to achieving high
303 resolution in nanopores. This was achieved using high ionic strength (3 M LiCl) and
304 low pH (3), and by constricting the pore with addition of an aromatic residue in the
305 pore channel (FraC^{G13F}). A greater cation congregation around the sampling region of
306 FraC tuned the electrostatic barrier in the pore, allowing a stronger interaction between
307 the peptide and the nanopore. High ionic strengths also reduce electrophoretic flow
308 across the pore, further slowing peptide translocation. The effects of ionic strength
309 vary depending on the charge characteristics of the peptide and nanopore used. PTM
310 observations can be visualized by plotting the current drop against the counts of single
311 molecules translocating through the pore (**Figure 5c**). Either an additional peak at a
312 new current amplitude is observed when plotting all the counts, or an existing peak
313 becomes shifted. The glycosylation study demonstrated the applicability of nanopores
314 to general PTM detection, and the principles illustrated here have been applied to
315 mutations and PTMs in aggregation prone proteins.

316
317 This generalizability was demonstrated in neurodegeneration-related studies, where
318 PTMs of the C-terminus of α S were discerned within a biological α -hemolysin (α HL)

319 nanopore⁷⁸. Another study demonstrated whole protein evaluation, discerning both
320 PTMs and mutations of the α S protein in an aerolysin nanopore⁴⁰. The size limitation
321 for this precision level still applied, however, and monomeric samples had to be
322 cleaved enzymatically prior to measurements to produce fragments small enough for
323 this detailed analysis. The differences between cleaved wild-type and mutant/PTM
324 samples were identified by changes in the dwell time and current blockade profiles for
325 the cleaved samples.

326

327 Beyond sequence-level studies of aggregation-prone proteins, biological nanopores
328 have been used in studying the aggregation of A β 42³⁵. While small A β 42 monomers
329 could translocate through the pore, aggregates blocked current across a α HL
330 nanopore via interactions with the pore opening but were too large to move through it
331 (**Figure 5d**). Lower signal amplitudes were observed for a small oligomer pore
332 blockade versus a larger oligomer pore blockade, while larger protofibrils resulted in
333 bumping signals when they impacted the pore but could not engage with the aperture.
334 These blockade and bumping profiles could be used to characterize the aggregation
335 process to an extent, allowing probing of the aggregation system in the presence of
336 various effectors. Aggregation reactions were carried out and the samples extracted
337 for nanopore analysis.

338

339 Similar work on α S aggregates characterized the influence of a disaccharide
340 (trehalose) on wild-type and mutant A53T α S protofilament formation in an α -HL
341 nanopore⁷⁵. The challenges in that study included lack of full translocation for larger
342 aggregates and membrane leakage induced by α S oligomer insertion into the lipid
343 bilayer the pores were embedded in. This illustrates the unique problems that oligomer
344 measurements can present, and a disadvantage of using biological nanopore
345 systems. Nonetheless, the researchers were able to obtain reproducible metrics of the
346 aggregation process via signals from α S oligomer engagement with the outer pore
347 vestibule which produced larger current blockades/bumps. They found that trehalose
348 reduced protofibril formation, overlapping with prior research that found that it
349 ameliorated huntingtin aggregation⁷⁹. Biological nanopores can therefore be employed
350 as an effective platform for study of oligomerization levels in some cases.

351

352 Overall, biological nanopores are extremely useful in obtaining sequence-level peptide
353 information and have seen some use in investigating the aggregation process. Future
354 developments could see them used for the highly sensitive detection of disease-
355 related PTMs in patient blood samples, which could be implemented in compact
356 biological nanopore devices such as the MinION, developed by ONT⁸⁰. The recently
357 published biomarker test for p-tau217 in Alzheimer's disease would be an impactful
358 application of this technology⁸¹. The area of aggregate study remains dominated by
359 solid-state nanopores, due to the possibility to tailor the pore diameter to the size
360 distribution of the oligomers of interest. While this approach enables full translocation,
361 it carries the caveat that some signal resolution is lost, especially in the wider
362 nanopores. However, most neurological oligomers fall within a size range that allows
363 high resolution of all particles that translocate, except monomers. It is generally
364 preferable to increase the nanopore diameter enough to avoid detection of monomers
365 in any case, which are a major source of noise in nanopore measurements.

366 367 **[H1] Solid-state nanopores for label-free investigations**

368
369 There are two categories of solid-state nanopores, which can be separated by their
370 method of manufacture. Solid-state nanopores can be fabricated via the creation of a
371 pore in silicon nitride (SiN) substrate using an electron beam⁴⁶, or the pulling of glass
372 nanopipettes. Owing to the small thickness of SiN films (10s-100s nm) pores made via
373 this route have a very low aspect ratio, or a larger diameter relative to the length of the
374 pore channel, which gives higher signal resolution (**Figure 2b**). Nanopipettes have a
375 higher aspect ratio, which reduces resolution, although the conical architecture has
376 the benefit of channeling particles towards the pore aperture (**Figure 2c**). SiN pores
377 are more expensive to manufacture than nanopipettes, more challenging to reproduce
378 than nanopipettes and more likely to foul than nanopipettes, especially in the low pore
379 diameter range. Glass nanopipettes offer the advantage of cheaper manufacture,
380 lower risk of fouling and more reliable pore sizing but with a reduction of resolution
381 due to higher aspect ratio. Nanopipettes are considered the best compromise for
382 scaling up use of solid-state nanopores in oligomer detection, given they are highly
383 sensitive but substantially cheaper to make⁴⁸. Sequence-level resolution is typically
384 lost in the wider pore required for aggregate translocation, but the size of an oligomer
385 particle can still be accurately measured, with tuning to the distribution of interest.

386 Monomers, oligomers and fibrils can be differentiated using the relative current
387 blockade and the dwell time.

388

389 The hurdles in studying unlabeled oligomers within solid-state nanopores are the rapid
390 speed of their translocation and noisy signals from unclear translocations. In
391 neurodegenerative oligomer studies, initial efforts focused on manipulation of solution
392 conditions to enhance resolution of these challenging analytes (**Figure 6a**). Amyloid
393 formation of lysozyme was studied in solid-state nanopores (0.5 M KCl, pH 2 in
394 nanopipettes)⁶⁸. A lysozyme aggregation time course was measured, detecting an
395 increase in large amplitude events over time. Lowering the pH increased the repulsion
396 between the amyloid fibrils and the nanopore walls reduced clogging due to van der
397 Waals interactions and allowed for the observation of enough events for an accurate
398 statistical analysis. Tuning experimental conditions in this way is an inexpensive
399 solution to the problem of clogging compared with surface treatment. A model for the
400 passage of a rod through a cylindrical pore was also designed, which was consistent
401 with the observed event distribution, and results were also cross referenced with AFM
402 which confirmed the size distributions of the aggregates observed⁶⁸.

403

404 In a follow-on study into lysozyme and β -lactoglobulin, a lower pH was used for
405 lysozyme measurements, while using neutral pH for β -lactoglobulin (1 M KCl, pH 2
406 and pH 7 in SiN nanopores)⁸². With good agreement, the amyloid fibril dimensions
407 obtained from nanopore measurements matched those from AFM. Differentiation of
408 amyloid derived from the two different proteins was possible based on the current
409 blockade profiles. Abnormally structured amyloid were also detected, with the potential
410 for specific fibril polymorph differentiation. This is relevant to disease diagnosis where
411 different diseases may yield distinct polymorphs⁸³.

412

413 Aggregation-prone proteins present a challenge for nanopore-based detection, as it is
414 important to use conditions that both slow the particles enough for measurement while
415 also allowing a clean translocation, without adhesion or pore blockage. Enhancing
416 current bandwidth improves the time resolution of measurements^{84,85}. Beyond
417 improved electronics, the introduction of chemical coatings customized for the target
418 of interest may slow down translocation (**Figure 6b**). Both the speed and noise of α S

419 oligomer translocation can be reduced by using polysorbate 20 (Tween 20) coated
420 silicon-nitride nanopores, for example⁷². Tween 20 is a non-ionic surfactant and
421 detergent which is used to reduce non-specific binding. The layer creates interactions
422 with the translocating particle which slow it down, but which also prevent aggregate
423 adhesion to the pore surface and channel blockage. This leads to cleaner
424 translocations and more reproducible signals.

425

426 Combining surface chemistry with tailored pH approaches exhibited improved signal
427 resolution and reduced fouling owing to adsorption of hydrophobic amyloid to the pore
428 surface (1 M KCl, pH 2.7)⁸⁶. A conical pore model of particle translocation was also
429 proposed⁸⁶. Chemical etching followed by functionalization of the internal surface of a
430 conical pore via track-etching of a PET film with PEG allowed clean β -lactoglobulin
431 amyloid measurements. The hydrophilic PEG coating repelled β -lactoglobulin
432 oligomers, which improved signal resolution and extended the life of the nanopore
433 from days to weeks⁸⁶. One should note that oligomers and amyloid reduce device
434 lifespan, given particle adsorption can rapidly foul high precision devices. Taking
435 advantage of surface chemistry and solution conditions to combat this is key to
436 enabling widespread adoption of nanopore-based sensing in oligomer detection.

437

438 Characterization of the size, shape and abundance of the oligomers of α S has been
439 reported using solid-state nanopores with anti-fouling surface chemistry³⁹. To achieve
440 this goal, a negative voltage was applied which resulted in positive resistive pulses as
441 particles translocated through the pore. A state-of-the-art nanopore coating was used
442 to prevent non-specific binding: poly(acrylamide) poly(2-methyl-2-oxazoline)
443 hexaneamine propyldimethylethoxysilane PAcrAm-g-(PMOXA, NH₂, Si). The size and
444 shape of individual α S oligomers, ranging from one to 122 monomers, was
445 characterized (**Figure 6b,c**)³⁹. The size distribution correlated with results found via
446 techniques such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and mass photometry.
447 The shape of α S oligomers can provide crucial information about their toxicity and
448 membrane damaging activity. Thus, the researchers took a further step of assessing
449 this property (**Figure 6d**). The shape and morphology of the oligomers derived from
450 nanopore measurements were in agreement with previous measurements using lower
451 throughput, higher resolution techniques such as cryogenic electron microscopy (cryo-

452 EM)³⁹. The researchers also measured the abundance of oligomers in solution which
453 ranged from 50 pM to 2.4 nM. These results highlight the ability of nanopores to
454 overcome conventional oligomer characterization challenges such as transience, low
455 concentration, instrument fouling, accurate sizing and detailed morphological
456 characterization.

457

458 The capacity of nanopores to analyze several different features of oligomers at scale
459 has enabled studies into disease relevant oligomers in a more efficient manner. α S
460 mutants A30P and E46K were reported to have higher oligomerization propensity
461 compared to the wild-type, as shown with a 5 nm silicon nitride pore⁴³. The size of
462 oligomers was observed via the magnitude of the nanopore translocation events over
463 an aggregation time course (6, 12 and 15 days) (**Figure 6e**). At the start of the
464 experiment, the sample was monomeric and so no translocation was observed. As
465 aggregation occurred, each particle translocation was observed as a current drop, the
466 size and duration of which correspond to the size and shape of the particle. At later
467 timepoints more and larger translocation signals were observed due to the larger and
468 more numerous aggregates. These results were complemented with TEM of the
469 aggregates formed in each sample. Taken together, the findings suggested that the
470 oligomers largely populated three groups of discrete size. These conclusions partially
471 corroborated other work carried out with an array of measurement techniques
472 including HPLC-SEC, analytical ultracentrifugation, cryo-EM and AFM, which
473 identified two subpopulations of oligomers⁸⁷. The nanopore study illustrated how
474 nanopore-based detection can provide information that previously required the use of
475 multiple techniques to verify.

476

477 Different oligomer subtypes were also identified in a Tween 20 functionalized
478 nanopore study of α S aggregation in the presence of negatively charged 1,2-dioleoyl-
479 sn-glycero-3-[phospho-L-serine] (DOPS) small unilamellar vesicles (SUVs)⁷². The
480 SUVs were found to increase the formation of oligomers, adding evidence to the well
481 documented link between lipid membranes and α S aggregation (**Figure 6f**)^{88,89}.
482 Although the extent to which the oligomer subpopulations observed in vitro relate to
483 physiological disease processes remains largely unknown, the ability of nanopores to
484 probe these questions will be useful in future efforts to define physiological

485 oligomerization processes. These studies demonstrate how nanopores can reveal
486 which factors strongly influence the aggregation process.

487

488 The adhesive property of oligomers has been used as a metric in of itself. A study into
489 A β 42 oligomers using a glass nanopipette investigated this highly aggregation-prone
490 peptide⁹⁰. Particle adhesion to the nanopore surface was most pronounced for
491 oligomeric samples via analysis of the ion current rectification of glass nanopores
492 (**Figure 6g**). This finding was compared to monomeric or fibrillar samples, which
493 exhibited lower adhesion. As oligomers were found to be metastable, the adhesive
494 property of A β 42 oligomers was suggested to be associated with their low stability, as
495 the solvent-exposed hydrophobic surface area may promote adhesion to available
496 surfaces. This property was further speculated to relate to a toxic mechanism by which
497 oligomers interfere with cell processes through non-specific hydrophobic
498 interactions⁹⁰.

499

500 Nanopore methods have considerable potential for discerning aggregation
501 mechanisms, an important area of study for understanding how protein misfolding
502 diseases progress at the molecular level. Multiple studies established the kinetic
503 theory behind protein aggregation, validated with complex experimental methods for
504 a few key aggregation systems^{45,7,21,50,91-94}. Mechanism elucidation currently requires
505 a combination of fluorescence-tracked aggregation kinetics assays, each isolating a
506 mechanistic step such as primary nucleation, secondary nucleation or fragmentation,
507 and elongation, followed by confirmation via TIRF microscopy⁹⁵ or radiolabeled
508 aggregation assays⁹⁶. Aggregation mechanisms are also strongly dependent on
509 solution conditions, and the surfaces available^{97,98}. Each pipeline is a series of
510 complex and lengthy measurements, which could be streamlined using nanopores.
511 Oligomer measurements are the most challenging aspect of mechanism validation,
512 and given their efficacy in this regard, nanopores should see more widespread use
513 here. One study suggested that secondary mechanisms of aggregation dominate for
514 A β 42 based on observations of high oligomer levels in samples where monomer is
515 incubated with preformed fibrils⁴⁵. Current profiles were also used to differentiate
516 between different mutant aggregate polymorphs of A β 42 and α S. That analysis

517 demonstrated that the use of nanopores can achieve an unambiguous and efficiently
518 obtained dataset for the fitting of the aggregation mechanism of a particular system.

519
520 Another key aggregation target in Alzheimer's disease, tau, has been given particular
521 attention. The influence of cofactors (heparin)³⁷ has been studied on the single
522 aggregate level (**Figure 6f**). In that study, the disease-associated P301L mutant was
523 found to promote both higher oligomerization levels and a fibril breakage mechanism
524 (fragmentation), when aggregation is induced by heparin³⁷. The P301L tau mutant was
525 reported to have higher aggregate conformational flexibility than the wild-type, via the
526 signal fluctuation observed as particles translocated. Heparin had previously been
527 found to induce fibril formation of tau, alongside other polyanionic molecules such as
528 RNA and polyglutamate, which can neutralize the positive charge of tau, allowing it to
529 aggregate more easily⁹⁹. Increased fragmentation leads to aggregate proliferation
530 owing to the increased number of fibril ends available for elongation. This mechanism
531 was discerned from the population analysis and from the current enhancement
532 observed in the current blockade. The study represents an effective use of nanopores
533 for mechanism discernment. Nanopores could provide insights into mechanistic
534 changes as a function of disease relevant conditions in work to come⁵⁰.

535
536 Label-free nanopore-based sensing has potential for protein oligomer
537 characterization, but challenges remain for its effective implementation. Signals
538 arising from nanopore-based detection are complex, leading to difficulty in data
539 analysis and, by extension, throughput. Achieving good signal resolution is challenging
540 owing to the high speed of particle translocations. Solid-state nanopores have also not
541 yet seen incorporation into devices that could be widely distributed in the way
542 biological nanopores have.

543 544 **[H1] Advancing the field**

545
546 The technical difficulties surrounding distribution and uptake of solid-state nanopore-
547 based sensing could be solved across many use cases by innovative device design
548 and combination with other novel technologies. To address the problem of data
549 analysis, machine learning (ML) methods are being employed. Approaching the
550 problem from the experimental side, label-based methods can resolve many of the

551 measurement issues discussed. Advantages from DNA nanostructure labelling
552 include comparative ease of analysis, greater throughput due to multiplexing, and the
553 higher resolution resulting from use of polyanionic tags which slow translocation. Novel
554 device design also provides more efficient diagnostic tools for protein misfolding
555 diseases, such as the real time fast amyloid seeding and translocation (RT-FAST)
556 class of detection devices.

557

558 [H2] Real time fast amyloid seeding and translocation (RT-FAST)

559

560 Solid-state nanopore sensing is a potential diagnostic device for patient samples
561 containing disease-associated α S and A β 42 aggregates^{17,44,67}. RT-FAST achieved a
562 faster detection timescale than the α S RT-QuIC assay, reducing the read-out time
563 from many hours to 90 minutes⁴⁴. This was possible owing to the higher sensitivity of
564 nanopore-based detection to the presence of low levels of oligomers compared with
565 the RT-QuIC fluorescence readout, thus allowing detection of aggregate accrual much
566 earlier (**Figure 7a**). Accurate estimation of the initial aggregate concentration present
567 in the sample was also possible. This achievement was particularly notable, as the
568 aggregation reaction and the nanopore measurement were all carried out within one
569 device. However, while the RT-QuIC assay was validated against patient aggregate
570 samples, the RT-FAST assay was in this case only tested against pure, artificially-
571 generated aggregates. RT-FAST was successfully applied to measurement of
572 artificially generated A β 42 seeds in 4% CSF. The researchers tailored the surface
573 chemistry by functionalization with L-DOPA to reduce adsorption of the more
574 hydrophobic A β 42 oligomers compared to α S⁶⁷.

575

576 While this development is promising, maintaining the speed and performance
577 improvement when measuring patient-derived aggregate samples is essential. In the
578 A β 42 use-case, the measurement took 180 minutes, but this was extended in the
579 presence of CSF. Improvements will require optimization of both the solution and
580 surface chemistries involved. It remains to be seen whether RT-FAST will be capable
581 of differentiating disease conditions in the way that RT-QuIC can, though the
582 previously described differentiation of fibril polymorphs in nanopores demonstrates the

583 feasibility of this. Given RT-QuIC is a commercialized diagnostic method, any
584 improvements in this area will have a tangible benefit to patients.

586 [H2] DNA nanostructure labelling

587
588 While label-free methods can give a measure of protein aggregation levels in a
589 sample, discerning single-monomer or oligomer events at high resolution in a
590 heterogeneous environment is challenging without a distinctive translocation
591 signature. Since biological samples have a complex composition, to differentiate signal
592 arising from any other components, one could turn to DNA-based oligomer labelling.
593 Labelling allows customization of the readout using shape-specific DNA
594 nanostructures attached to the analyte, which create distinctive signatures as they
595 translocate through the nanopore. This approach has been demonstrated using
596 antibody-conjugated magnetic beads with DNA nanostars for readouts, in a set up that
597 mimics ELISA but with much higher sensitivity¹⁰⁰. DNA nanostructures can be digitally
598 encoded with DNA dumbbells and attached to the analyte to allow clear detection,
599 allowing for quantification of binding affinities of DNA-binding protein complexes³⁴.

600
601 An initial effort in this area was a study characterizing the interaction of α S with lipid
602 membranes enabled by a trapping lipid-bound α S adjacent to an α HL pore (**Figure**
603 **7b**)⁴¹. A single-stranded DNA oligonucleotide, oligo(dC30), was covalently linked to
604 the cysteine in an α S mutant (A140C). α S interacted with the adjacent membrane to
605 the pore while the attached DNA acted as a reporter via interactions with the nanopore.
606 By observing the blockade current amplitudes and dwell time of the negatively-
607 charged oligo(dC30) as it was threaded into the pore, the researchers studied the
608 dynamics of the binding of the modified α S to the adjacent lipid membrane. Binding
609 interactions were observed in the presence of two metal ions, Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . Zn^{2+}
610 appeared to lead to longer dwell times of lipid-bound α S, stabilizing the interaction, as
611 well as a less compact conformation when compared to Cu^{2+} or the control condition.
612 The effects of ligands such as dopamine and peptidomimetics were also studied,
613 providing a potential platform for screening for modulators of the α S-lipid interaction,
614 which is key to pathogenic oligomerization.

616 The concept of a DNA tag can be expanded upon via DNA nanotechnology through
617 creation of more complex structures with identifying information. The field of DNA
618 nanotechnology involves using the information the DNA encodes to assemble
619 structural motifs which can then be connected¹⁰¹. Using this concept, one can design
620 molecular constructs that can enhance the specificity and sensitivity of solid-state
621 nanopore sensing (**Figure 7c,d**)¹⁰². In **Figure 7c**, a dsDNA strand with overhangs is
622 used as a scaffold for DNA aptamers which can bind to α S aggregates. The passage
623 of the DNA through the pore creates a characteristic drop in current, which returns to
624 baseline once the full DNA strand has passed through the pore aperture. If an aptamer
625 is bound to an oligomer, a greater drop in current is observed as a downward spike
626 attached to the DNA signal, which is proportional to the size of the oligomer.
627 Combining nanopore sensing with DNA nanotechnology maintains synthetic and
628 technological simplicity and straightforward design while increasing detection abilities.
629 By adding 2D DNA structures such as DNA dumbbells to a linear backbone DNA single
630 strand one can digitally encode the structures (**Figure 7d**). In much the same way a
631 protein creates a signal spike as it passes through the pore, the DNA dumbbells create
632 a drop in the current signal where a dumbbell is present (a '1') or less of a drop where
633 a linear spacer is present (a '0'). In this way DNA nanostructures can be used to
634 uniquely tag protein oligomers.

635

636 The backbone of DNA nanostructure is typically a 7.2 kbp ssDNA fragment derived
637 from an M13mp18 phage vector. It has been demonstrated, for DNA data storage, that
638 at least 56 such bits (dumbbells) can be incorporated into this structure and read out
639 in a nanopore¹⁰³. 2^{56} tags could therefore be detected concurrently in a single
640 measurement, substantially higher than the multiplexing limit for fluorophores (4-5).
641 To translate this to oligomer detection, the pore size and DNA tag size would both
642 need to be optimized for the oligomers of interest. While the multiplex capacity would
643 be potentially lower than that of the DNA data storage example, it would likely remain
644 orders of magnitude above current fluorescence methods.

645

646 The key advantage of this approach lies in assigning a unique barcode to every
647 oligomer sample. This provides clear identification of the origin of a sample, and allows
648 the mixing of samples from different conditions, and simultaneous measurement.

649 Consequently, this method facilitates the examination of oligomer populations with a
650 finer level of detail and at a higher throughput than was previously achievable. The
651 multiplex capability may be crucial for oligomer detection, where current approaches
652 are only capable of lengthy measurements in series. The demonstrated utility of
653 combining solid-state nanopores with digitally-encoded DNA nanostructures for highly
654 multiplexed detection of single molecules could underpin future large scale oligomer
655 studies^{34,70,104}.

656

657 Two approaches to date leveraged nanostructure tagging of proteins for solid-state
658 nanopore sensing, both using glass nanopipettes. In the first approach, the DNA
659 nanostructure contained an aptamer with an affinity for the target of interest (**Figure**
660 **7c**). Two studies used this approach, one targeted at monomeric proteins¹⁰⁴ and one
661 targeted at α S oligomers¹⁷. The former study provided a proof-of-principle that this
662 approach could be generally applied to monomeric protein systems such as α -
663 thrombin and acetylcholinesterase (AChE). Detection was possible in the background
664 of human serum samples without need for washing or use of concentrated antibody.
665 The latter study was explicitly aimed at providing a highly sensitive diagnostic for
666 Parkinson's disease via detection of α S oligomer levels in patient samples¹⁷.

667

668 The key benefit of aptamer approaches is the lack of specific functionalization of the
669 α S oligomers. Potential mass production of aptamer-nanostructure constructs also
670 makes this approach scalable. A drawback is the lower assurance of specific binding
671 and successful multiplexing, since the non-covalent interaction can be disrupted by
672 competing interactions, allowing tag interchange¹⁷. Finding a highly specific binder for
673 α S oligomers is a goal of research into Parkinson's disease, but it remains elusive¹⁰⁵.
674 The structures of oligomers have hydrophobic exposed areas which promote non-
675 specific interactions¹⁰⁶⁻¹⁰⁸. Nonetheless, the aptamer approach showed effective
676 differentiation of patients who had disease (n=5) from those who did not (n=5) in this
677 study. The combination of aptamers and DNA nanostructures, together with RT-FAST,
678 may represent the next generation of highly sensitive biomarker detection methods for
679 neurodegeneration. Earlier detection in these slow-moving and initially asymptomatic
680 diseases is critical to successful intervention.

681

682 Covalent tagging is an alternative to aptamer-based binding. When the tags must not
683 interchange or potentially interact with other components of a sample, covalent
684 modification offers a safer route. In a recent example, N122C α S was functionalized
685 with an azide moiety and aggregated, before click labelling with a dibenzocyclooctyne
686 (DBCO) tagged nanostructure and measured (**Figure 7d**)³⁰. The tagged oligomers
687 gave distinct signals as they translocated. It was possible to mix multiple samples and
688 measure them simultaneously in the nanopore, by ensuring each sample had its own
689 unique nanostructure tag (**Figure 7d**)⁶⁶.

690
691 The covalent binding approach was employed to differentiate the effects of small
692 molecule inhibitors of α S oligomer formation^{30,55,65,109}. The goal was to allow multiple
693 inhibitor samples to be measured in the same nanopore, at the same time, thus
694 increasing throughput for a screening strategy. Covalent tagging removed the risk of
695 label interchange, which was essential for accurate determination of oligomer levels if
696 the samples were to be mixed. The possibility of monomer interchange was removed
697 via high dilution prior to mixing. This procedure enabled accurate differentiation of the
698 aggregation inhibitors, which matched the ranking of the same inhibitors in another
699 method, μ FFE, where the measurements had been carried out in series⁶⁵. This
700 approach offers the potential for high-throughput analysis of a challenging target, in
701 turn providing a beneficial impact on therapeutic programs focused on targeting these
702 protein aggregates.

703
704 A key consideration that remains to be fully explored is the sensitivity of nanopores to
705 background components in a sample. These components can clog the pores leading
706 to current fluctuations that mask the analyte signal. A biofluid such as human serum
707 contains thousands of different proteins, often at higher concentrations than the target
708 analyte making detection challenging. Dilution is a strategy that has worked well. In
709 the above examples utilizing aptamer-based nanostructures, detection of spiked
710 thrombin and AChE in human serum and native α S oligomers in CSF, required a 20-
711 fold dilution in the former case, and a 50-fold dilution in the latter to achieve stable
712 current baselines. Given human serum is both a more common sample than CSF, and
713 a more densely populated one in terms of protein components, achieving detection of
714 native samples, rather than spiked ones, would demonstrate the capacity of

715 nanopores as a generalizable diagnostic. Significant dilutions could create issues
716 where the analyte is already present at extremely low concentrations, especially where
717 non-covalent strategies are used, and the aptamer affinity is too low to achieve
718 effective binding. As such a key goal of future work in this area is a nanopore device
719 that can tolerate higher background and still achieve sensitive readouts. Research into
720 surface chemistries and solid-state pore architectures could potentially achieve this.

721

722 [H2] Machine learning

723

724 Machine learning (ML) methods are transforming the amount of information that can
725 be extracted from the analysis of nanopore measurements^{110,111}. ONT has popularized
726 the deep learning approach to accurately sequence DNA in nanopores^{110,111}. In their
727 initial implementation, DeepMod, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) were employed to
728 identify the DNA base translocating through the pore, based on training data. They
729 have recently reported that further improvement can be achieved using the
730 transformer architecture (DeepMod2)¹¹¹. ML enables the determination of both polyA
731 tail length and RNA secondary structure features in nanopores, which would be
732 extremely challenging to discern with any accuracy using manual analysis¹¹². Further
733 applications include detection of PTMs of the C-terminus of α S within an α HL
734 nanopore using RNNs, and a coronavirus-sensing platform that could distinguish
735 different variants^{78,113}.

736

737 The application of ML carries the caveat of extensive data curation requirements, and
738 the expertise and time needed to successfully train models. Complex training data
739 may require a long process of architecture optimization¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁶. In the case of nanopore
740 sensing, the signal generated by a particle translocating through a pore is influenced
741 by many factors including the orientation of entry, interactions with other particles in
742 the pore, the size and charge of the particles, whether any initial docking with the pore
743 entrance occurs, and whether any conformational changes are required for the particle
744 to translocate¹¹⁷.

745

746 ML has also been applied to DNA nanostructure tagged data. The signals are first
747 processed using simple sorting algorithms, which is possible due to the higher signal

748 to noise in labelled data. After this, model training on the processed data is more facile
749 as signals are simpler to interpret. This was achieved recently using a convolutional
750 neural network (CNN), an architecture well suited to image recognition. The barcode
751 signal can be used to identify events that are then fed into the CNN as an image. A
752 CNN can then categorize which events have a certain barcode if a multiplexed sample
753 is used, or predict characteristics of the peak resulting from the translocation of the
754 particle attached to the barcode¹¹⁸. It remains an investment to develop such a tool,
755 but a less demanding one than in the case of unlabeled data.

756 757 **[H2] Future development prospects**

758
759 Nanopores have plenty of potential in the field of oligomer detection. Key to realizing
760 those possibilities is the industrial scale manufacture of solid-state nanopores, and
761 integration into commercially available devices, as has already been achieved for
762 biological nanopores, and demonstrated by the RT-FAST platform. Research into
763 appropriate surface chemistries and solution conditions to use with different oligomeric
764 proteins would also provide customizable options for each use case. Combination with
765 technologies such as DNA nanostructure tagging, and ML based signal analysis will
766 drastically expand the speed and scale of oligomer detection that is currently possible.

767 768 **[H1] Conclusion and Outlook**

769
770 The advances that we reviewed demonstrate the flexibility of nanopores for explorative
771 investigations and their potential high-throughput screening and diagnostic platforms.
772 Key challenges, including exact discernment of monomers, dimers, and higher-order
773 oligomers, remain a difficulty with large solid-state pores, while measurement of larger
774 aggregates is restricted with smaller biological pores. Engineering high-resolution
775 solid-state pores with tuneable diameters may be the key to solving these issues.
776 Mass production of nanopores with customizable diameters appropriate to the users'
777 needs and at reasonable cost will be crucial in this respect. Accurately identifying and
778 quantifying each oligomeric state requires high-resolution analysis and experimental
779 techniques that are still under development. Variability in solid-state nanopore
780 fabrication can also lead to inconsistencies in pore size and shape, affecting the
781 reproducibility of experiments and the comparability of results across different studies.

782 Improved fabrication techniques are needed to bring solid-state nanopore
783 reproducibility on par with that of biological nanopores. Besides the hardware itself,
784 preparation of oligomer samples for nanopore analysis can be complex and time-
785 consuming, given the sensitivity of both the instrument and analyte. Robust protocols
786 and user-friendly devices are required to reduce the need for highly trained specialists.

787
788 Work on these challenges has already begun, including the significant work on solution
789 conditions, pore architecture, surface chemistries, and signal analysis already
790 discussed. Highlights include the work done in the machine learning space to ease
791 signal analysis such as QuipuNet¹¹⁸, and the measurements done in biosamples such
792 as serum and CSF^{17,104}. Much more can be done, however, especially in the
793 manufacturing space to improve solid-state nanopore consistency and expand their
794 availability. Provided these challenges can be met, nanopore sensing offers solutions
795 to many of the challenges posed by the detection and quantification of protein
796 oligomers. It has the potential to offer rapid answers to fundamental research
797 questions about aggregation mechanisms in vitro and in vivo, as well as effective
798 aggregate binding or inhibitor screening platforms, and diagnostic devices for
799 misfolding diseases. These solutions are urgently needed given the current
800 intractability of many protein oligomer systems and the diseases associated with them.
801 As the first signs of success in decades are beginning to appear for the study of
802 neurodegenerative diseases, both in diagnostics and treatments, nanopore sensing is
803 well placed to lead a revolution in our capacity to quantitatively assess these
804 conditions.

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1192 RIH and SES researched and wrote the article, all authors reviewed and edited the
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1195 **Competing Interests**

1196 No competing interests.

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1205 **Figure 1. Misfolded protein oligomers and their association with Alzheimer's**
1206 **and Parkinson's diseases. (A)** Functional oligomers have roles in inflammatory
1207 responses, DNA repair and cell membrane proteins. Inflammasomes are multi-protein
1208 complexes in the innate immune system, which can be activated by antibiotics such
1209 as daptomycin¹¹⁹. These oligomers are consistently structured and tend to have a
1210 relatively low and well-defined number of monomer constituents. **(B)** Aberrant
1211 oligomers are often formed from intrinsically disordered proteins, such as α -synuclein.
1212 These oligomers are heterogeneous and interact deleteriously with cellular
1213 components, before maturing into amyloid fibrils. **(C)** Comparison of a healthy neuron
1214 with a neuron affected by **(D)** Alzheimer's disease, where A β aggregates
1215 extracellularly into amyloid plaques and tau aggregates intracellularly into
1216 neurofibrillary tangles, and with a neuron affected by **(E)** Parkinson's disease, where
1217 α -synuclein assembles into Lewy bodies. **(F)** Oligomer formation and potential
1218 mechanism of toxicity in Parkinson's disease via mitochondrial membrane damage
1219 and complex I inhibition, leading to opening of the mitochondrial permeability transition
1220 pore (mPTP) and activation of caspase 3-dependent apoptosis⁴². ROS: reactive
1221 oxygen species.

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Figure 2. Comparison of different types of nanopores used for oligomer detection. (A) Biological nanopores are commercially available as DNA sequencing devices, where each nanopore protein has identical shape and diameter. Typical diameters are ~1-4 nm, which is ideal for characterizing small, unfolded polypeptide chains and their post-translational modifications (PTMs). Negatively-charged peptides are measured in the example shown, which are driven through the pore from the negative electrode to the positive electrode. The direction of the current must be tailored ahead of time to the charge of the analyte in question. (B) Synthetic solid-state nanopores can be functionalized, and having an adjustable diameter in the ~1-100 nm range they are suitable for larger protein oligomers and fibrils. Silicon (Si) and silicon nitride (SiN) are commonly used materials for the synthetic films in which the pores are created. The pore size is adjustable but challenging to control when using electron beams. (C) Nanopipettes are conical solid-state nanopores with a relatively inert glass substrate that can be functionalized via etching methods. The conical shape may be used to achieve higher signal-to-noise ratios during measurements and pore size is adjustable. (D) Schematic of a raw nanopore trace with molecules translocating, a single molecule translocation is referred to as an event. Example events are boxed in red, for different sizes of oligomer. Each particle movement through the pore creates

1257 a current drop, the size and duration of which corresponds to the size of the particle
1258 and the speed of translocation. **(E)** Event characterization parameters used to
1259 describe events and gather information about size, shape and charge of a molecule
1260 include event integral, event duration and current blockade.

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Figure 3. Bulk methods for protein oligomer and large aggregate detection. (A) Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) followed by mass spectrometry (MS) or enzyme linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) provide a monomer equivalent concentration within each fraction collected from SEC⁵¹. These methods determine the average quantity for each fraction, and an approximation of the oligomer size based on elution volume. ELISA can be used without prior SEC separation when using the same antibody for both capture and detection, as only aggregates have enough epitopes to accommodate multiple binding. However, centrifugation is necessary to remove fibrils, and background signal is higher. **(B)** Real-time quaking-induced conversion (RT-QulC) takes aggregate samples and uses them to seed aggregation reactions of recombinant proteins in vitro, tracking the progress with amyloid binding dyes such as thioflavin T (ThT). This method gives an approximate value for the aggregates present in the starting sample based on the aggregation kinetics. Different aggregation profiles may be observed for different brain derived aggregates, which is used to differentiate disease conditions in patients.

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Figure 4. Single-molecule detection methods to characterize oligomers (A) confocal two-color coincidence detection⁶⁰ (TCCD), **(B)** fluorescence correlation spectroscopy⁶¹ (FCS) measurements, **(C)** single-molecule total internal reflection fluorescence⁶² (TIRF) imaging, **(D)** single-molecule spectrally-resolved points accumulation for imaging in nanoscale topography⁶³ (sPAINT), **(E)** atomic force microscopy^{59,11} (AFM, with example micrograph¹²⁰)^{64,121}, and **(F)** micro free-flow electrophoresis²³ (μ FFE). Parts of this figure were adapted from the authors' prior work^{122,123}. All examples given here correspond to applications of the corresponding technique to detection of protein oligomers.

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Figure 5. Biological nanopores for detection of post-translational modifications (PTMs), mutations, and the effect of different aggregation promoters or inhibitors. (A) A protein of interest containing a variant or PTM undergoes cleavage via protease into small fragments and (B) is fed into the nanopore. (C) The resulting plot of current measured versus event counts shows either the presence of additional peaks or an increase in peak size resulting from more events of the fragment of interest or a shift of current due to the fragment of interest vs the wild type. This will depend on the biological pore used and the fragment size as well as its charge. (D) Additionally, the effect of aggregation promoters and inhibitors has been tested in biological nanopores and results in different signature current traces. An A β 42 aggregation promoter resulted in more collisions rather than full current blockades due to the larger size of the aggregates, while inhibitors reduced the current blockade on average compared to the control due to the presence of fewer and smaller oligomers³⁵.

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Figure 6. Solid-state nanopores for protein aggregation and structure investigations. (A) Solution conditions are tailored to avoid protein fouling of the

1351 nanopore and lead to cleaner transitions⁶⁸. **(B)** Surface functionalization enhances
1352 event resolution and pore lifetime by reducing pore-aggregate adhesion and slowing
1353 pore transitions. Surface chemistry complexity ranges from simple hydrophilic
1354 coatings such as PEG to state-of-the-art coating solutions such as PAcrAm-g-
1355 PMOXA^{39,124}. **(C)** Aggregates of different sizes can be discerned and measured based
1356 on the volume measured in the nanopore as a result of translocation³⁹. **(D)** The shape
1357 of aggregates, e.g. elliptical or spherical, can be differentiated via observing the length-
1358 to-diameter ratio extracted from the current signal³⁹. **(E)** Time courses of nanopore
1359 translocations involve measuring the frequency of events at various time points, as
1360 well as the shift resulting from aggregates of larger diameters being formed which
1361 shifts the measured current over time⁴³. **(F)** The impact of aggregation effectors can
1362 be precisely studied in solid-state nanopores. Examples are small unilamellar vesicles
1363 (SUVs), which accelerated the rate of α S aggregation⁷², and heparin, which increased
1364 tau oligomerization levels and fibril breakage³⁷. **(G)** Particle adhesion to a nanopore
1365 glass surface has also been used as a metric, and was most pronounced for oligomeric
1366 samples⁹⁰.

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1385 **Figure 7. Advancing the field: Device design and DNA-tagged protein**
 1386 **measurements. (A)** The real-time fast amyloid seeding and translocation (RT-FAST)
 1387 assay can be used for the detection of α S or A β seeds of both WT and mutant variants
 1388 in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)^{44,67}. **(B)** DNA handles covalently linked to α S can be used
 1389 to study α S interactions with lipid membranes in biological nanopores⁴¹. The counts of
 1390 events and the corresponding current they induce vary depending on whether the
 1391 protein is bound or unbound to the membrane and the presence of effectors such as
 1392 ions. A histogram of the event counts vs the current value of each event is shown, with
 1393 a schematic raw trace below (note that the raw trace would have a higher absolute
 1394 residual current baseline with the effector added than without, as shown in the
 1395 histogram). In this case the effector pushes the current amplitude to higher magnitude
 1396 values, while also lowering the number of lipid binding events. The effector here is
 1397 Cu^{2+} , which changes the current observed at baseline, and also induces a more
 1398 compact α S structure that reduces lipid binding. **(C)** Phage λ DNA with overhangs can
 1399 be designed to form a DNA nanostructure containing an aptamer, which enables

1400 binding and study of proteins¹⁰⁴. Aggregate specific aptamers can be employed¹⁷. The
1401 passage of DNA through the pore creates a characteristic current drop, which lasts as
1402 long as the translocation of the DNA through the pore. If an oligomer is bound, a
1403 corresponding spike in current is observed in addition to the DNA signal. **(D)** M13
1404 phage DNA can be used as a backbone to create a nanostructure with features such
1405 as a dibenzocyclooctyne (DBCO) binding site and DNA dumbbells, which can be used
1406 for covalent modification of azide bearing biomolecules and to create barcodes for
1407 multiplexing, respectively³⁰. Depending on the diameter of the pore, multiple
1408 dumbbells packed together may be required to create a single spike. Spacers are
1409 needed between these dumbbell clusters to allow discernment of individual spikes.
1410 Replacing a barbell cluster with a spacer would be read as a '0', and would not yield
1411 a spike. A '11111' barcode is illustrated schematically (traces are generated, and not
1412 derived from experimental data).

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1414 **Summary**

1415 An overview of the progress and potential of nanopore-based detection of
1416 oligomerizing proteins is presented, covering the latest advances and combination
1417 with other emerging technologies including device design, DNA nanostructure tagging
1418 and ML enabled signal analysis.

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